

STORAGE RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURE ECO-SYSTEM

3rd TNA Call Documentation – User

USER REPORT (WITH SATISFACTION SURVEY): USER (S)

General information about the project	
Project title (as used in application)	High-temperature Hybrid Thermal Energy Storage
Project acronym (max 15 characters)	HiHyTES
StoRIES TNA RI(s) accessed	LIMCKA Labs
Keywords (up to ten, free text)	High Temperature Thermal Energy Storage, Latent Heat Storage, Phase Change Materials, Melting, Solidification, Computational Fluid Dynamics, High Performance Computing, Innovative Fin Designs
Arrival date (in town where RI located)	02 April 2024
Departure date (from town where RI located)	27 June 2024
Starting date of access (first day at RI)	02 April 2024
Finishing date of access (last day at RI)	27 June 2024
Number of days not using the RI (during the above period)	28 days
Reason for not using RI those days (describe)	Weekends (24 days), public holidays (4 days)
Number of days using the RI	59 days
Number of users granted access (group size)	2 persons
Comments	Only one user visited the RI, and the second user's role was only as an advisor.
Access Summary Report - work performed and initial results	
Brief description of the objectives of your project (up to 200 words)	
<p>The study investigates hybrid Thermal Energy Storage (TES) techniques for renewable energy and industrial applications to advance decarbonization efforts. TES plays a crucial role in stabilizing energy supply amidst the intermittent nature of renewables, yet challenges persist during charging and discharging phases. The proposed approach integrates latent and sensible heat storage</p>	

systems for high temperatures ($\sim 750^{\circ}\text{C}$) to mitigate operational limitations. Concentrated Solar Power (CSP) plants using Liquid Metals (LMs) as Heat Transfer Fluids (HTFs) and storage materials are examined with regard to their effectiveness at elevated temperatures. However, LMs encounter issues like higher heat diffusion in thermocline storage. Addressing this, the study suggests hybridizing with Phase Change Materials (PCMs) in Latent Heat Storage (LHS) systems, decreasing temperature on sensible heat storage tank, enhancing storage capacity, and facilitating isothermal heat exchange. The research endeavors to enhance the efficiency in LHS tanks using shell-and-tube designs with innovative minimal fin material. Various fin configurations (hollowed, perforated) are evaluated against conventional designs through numerical simulations using ANSYS Fluent, incorporating natural convection. The aim is to develop fin designs and PCM selections across different temperatures, crucial for improving cascaded LHS, PCM charging/discharging processes, and conducting detailed 3D CFD analyses for efficient high-power heat transfer with LMs.

Activities performed (up to 600 words)

Since the research aims to decrease the utilization of LM amount and so the volume of the thermocline storage tank, the research focuses on the development of a high-temperature LHS tank, but the thermocline tank is still crucial in the determination of LHS boundary conditions. The core of the study consists of the selection of PCMs, corrosion-resistant tube/shell materials, and especially the comparison of LMs and molten salts both as HTF and PCM. As CFD software, ANSYS Fluent was governed, and the enthalpy-porosity technique was approached after the melting/solidification option was activated. After a deep literature survey, boundary conditions, candidate materials, and geometry were determined. Then, since the CFD analysis requires high computational resources, the user learned how to create, submit, and run a job in a High Performance Computing (HPC) center of KIT.

Considering the potential and previous results of the thermocline system (the RI infrastructure has long years of experience with circulation loops and storage of LMs), the LHS storage tank boundary conditions were determined. Depending on the working temperature, two different HTFs were chosen that can operate at high temperatures up to 800°C : Liquid sodium (LM, high conductive) and FLiNaK (molten salt, low conductive). Especially focussing on the operation temperatures of the new generation CSP plants, MgCl_2 , aluminium, a commercial PCM, and Al-Si alloy (with gradually decreasing melting temperatures) were chosen to compare the melting/solidification performances. As a merit of the research, while salt PCMs were chosen to be enhanced via innovative fins, the other two metal PCMs completely filled the storage medium. The first step was to validate the numerical model via comparing it with the result of a 3D melting experiment from the literature. Then, considering the natural convection dynamics during the melting process, shell length, diameters of the shell and tube, and its ratio were determined. As a new possible idea for tube, shell, and fin material, utilization of Cu coated via Ni and Cr was offered in addition to Inconel alloy which is the only material studied in the literature. That is because of the corrosive nature of both HTF and PCM at elevated temperatures. Before starting the CFD simulations, the mesh independency was tested via three different node number. Subsequently, the model is also compared, testing with three different time step sizes. After the independence of the model was approved, tube and shell materials, HTFs, and the effect of mass flow rate on the melting process of MgCl_2 were investigated. Then, for the following simulations, liquid Na and Inconel alloy were chosen as HTF and shell/tube/fin material, respectively. The next step was to design innovative fin structures. Melting and solidification performances of the cases

with five different fin designs (perforated and hollowed) were compared with conventionally used 'Straight fin'. The examined parameters during these simulations are as follows: liquid fraction, PCM average temperature, outlet temperature, and heat flux. The results showed that it is inconvenient to use a cascaded LHS tank using multiple PCMs with decreasing melting temperatures. Hence, for our case study, the results showed that there is no need to design a cascaded LHS tank employing salt-based PCMs with fins. As an alternative, aluminium was used in order to show the different behaviour of metals as PCM during charging/discharging.

Scientific results (up to 800 words)

This part starts with documenting important details about the thermophysical properties of materials, geometries, inlet conditions, and boundary conditions set for all the simulations. Since both LMs and molten salts are used in the thermocline storage tanks, the performance of these two HTFs is also compared in the shell-and-tube LHS tanks. To assess a realistic condition, Inconel alloy is employed as a structural material whose properties are set up for shell, tube, and fin domains. As an alternative corrosive material, coated Cu (2mm Cu fin coated with 0.5mm Ni and 0.5mm Cr) is proposed even though such material has not been tested experimentally in the literature. MgCl₂ and Aluminium are employed as salt and metallic PCMs, respectively. The thermophysical properties (as temperature-dependent as possible) of HTFs, structural materials, and PCMs are given in Table 1-3. The same geometrical parameters (except fin/PCM ratio) are used for all fin designs, as depicted in Table 4. Absolute temperature is used in all temperature-dependent relations in the tables below.

Table 1: Thermophysical properties of HTFs

HTF	Density (kg/m ³)	Thermal Conductivity (W/mK)	Specific heat (J/kgK)	Dynamic viscosity (Pas)	Source
Liquid Na	966.74- 0.1274874 T- 5.38*10 ⁻⁵ T ²	98.91-0.046 T-3.714x10 ⁻⁶ T ²	1380	0.103 T ^{-0.9103}	[1]
Liquid FLiNaK	2018.9	0.921	1890	0.0029	[2]

Table 2: Thermophysical properties of structural materials

Structure Materials	Density (kg/m ³)	Thermal Conductivity (W/mK)	Specific heat (J/kgK)	Dynamic viscosity (Pas)	T _{melting} (°C)	Source
Inconel alloy 617	8360	24.2	586	-	-	[2]
Cu (50%)	8978	387.6	381	-	1083	[3]
Ni (25%)	8900	91.74	460	-	1452	[4]
Cr (25%)	7140	69.08	448	-	1830	[3]
<u>Coated Cu (weighted average)</u>	8499	168	417.5	-	-	Present Calculation

Table 3: Thermophysical properties of selected PCMs

PCMs	Melting point (°C)	Latent heat of fusion (kJ/kg)	Thermal Conductivity (W/mK)	Density (kg/m ³)	Specific heat (kJ/kgK)	Dynamic viscosity (Pas)	Source
MgCl ₂	714	452	0.46 (at 714°C)	2320 (at 25°C),	0.7602+1.6567 10 ⁻⁴ *T	0.0032	[5]

				1680 (at 714°C)			
Al	660	397	204	2375	0.89	0.0013	[6]

Table 4: Geometrical details of HEX and fin structures

HEX Geometry		Fin Geometry	
D _{tube_inner} (mm)	30	Fin/PCM ratio (%)	8.6
D _{tube_outer} (mm)	36	Fin Thickness (mm)	3
D _{shell_inner} (mm)	120	Annular Gap (mm)	42
D _{shell_outer} (mm)	126	Fin Length (mm)	37
D _{shell} /D _{tube}	3	Number of fins	8
Length(mm)	300		

The representative 3D view of the shell-and-tube LHS tank and 2D section views of innovative fin designs are demonstrated in Figure 1. Since there are two different PCMs used, to make a fair comparison, the temperature differences between $|T_{inlet}-T_{melting}|$ and $|T_{melting}-T_{inlet}|$ are kept constant for melting and solidification processes, as given in Table 5.

Here, only the most important results are reported due to the huge amount of data and graphs. The whole results will be published in journal papers.

Table 5: Initial and boundary conditions for selected PCMs during melting/solidification processes

MgCl₂			
Initial and Boundary Conditions for Melting (°C)		Initial and Boundary Conditions for Solidification (°C)	
T _{initial}	690	T _{initial}	738
T _{melting}	714	T _{melting}	714
T _{inlet}	750	T _{inlet}	678
Aluminum			
Initial and Boundary Conditions for Melting (°C)		Initial and Boundary Conditions for Solidification (°C)	
T _{initial}	636	T _{initial}	684
T _{melting}	660	T _{melting}	660
T _{inlet}	696	T _{inlet}	624

Figure 1: 3D view of shell-and-tube LHS tank and 2D section views of innovative fin designs.

1.HTF Selection

The first analysis uses coated Cu and Inconel alloy as tube and shell materials without fins, respectively. Figure 2 shows that if mass flow increases from 5 g/s to 7.5 g/s, heat flux is enhanced, but from 7.5g/s to 9g/s, there is no dramatic change in heat transfer performance.

Figure 2: Heat flux variation with different mass flow rates and HTFs during melting process.

Besides, using Liquid Na and molten salt causes almost the same heat flux results. However, as seen in Figure 3, there is a significant difference in outlet temperatures for different HTFs. This difference is because molten salt can carry a higher amount of thermal energy due to its superior density and specific heat values than liquid Na. The desired output temperature of the HTF leaving the LHS should be as low as possible for the stability of the thermocline tank in the hybrid concept envisaged in this study, as it would mean reduced thermal ratcheting. Therefore, the utilization of LM as HTF is preferred.

Figure 3: Outlet temperature variation with different mass flow rates and HTFs during melting process.

2. Structural Material Selection

In the following analyses, 5g/s mass flow rate is set.

In Figure 4, a comparison of the liquid fraction when using coated Cu and Inconel alloy, and when using liquid Na and molten salt during melting process is shown. Since the incident irradiation in CSP applications is not available for more than 8 hours, molten salt used cases with a 5g/s mass flow rate is not acceptable to reach the fully-melted phase. Moreover, there is a negligibly small difference in melting performance whether coated Cu or Inconel alloy is employed as tube material. Therefore, Inconel alloy will be used as shell/tube/fin material for the remaining analysis.

Figure 4: Variation of liquid fraction with different structural materials and HTFs during melting process.

3. Melting Performance of LHS Tank with Innovative Fin Designs

As shown in Figure 1, in addition to straight fin design, five different fin structure are proposed to enhance primarily melting process of PCM due to activating dominancy of natural convection. In cases 2-6, 20% of the fin material was first removed by designing the fin hollowed and perforated. As demonstrated in Figure 5, the attempts of decreasing fin material cause enhancement in melting performance, but none of them is still not as good as the 'Straight fin' case. Besides, the performance of Case 2 is the worst among all designs due to the high thermal resistance caused by the low contact area between the tube and fins. Afterwards, the perforated designs which show the best performances (Cases 4-6), removed further from 20% to 40%. The results uncover the extra 20% removal of fin material does not cause a dramatic decrease in melting performances, as seen in Figure 5.

A fair discussion can be done by examining the stored amount of thermal energy at the end of the melting process instead of liquid fraction results. Because the existence of fins means not only improved conduction heat transfer but also the occupation of storage volume. With less fin utilization, more PCM fills the tank. Figure 6 supports this idea; more heat can be stored when perforated fin structures are employed. In fact, the second-best cases are still perforated fin cases with 40% fin removal.

Figure 5: Variation of liquid fraction with different fin structures during melting process.

Figure 6: Total stored heat enthalpy at the end of 6 hours melting process.

4. Solidification Performance of LHS Tank with Innovative Fin Designs

Figure 7 demonstrates the solidification performances of the fin designs. A solid discussion can be made after the remaining uncompleted cases reach the fully-solidified phase, but the trend shows that the best designs in the solidification process are perforated fins again, similar to melting dynamics. Although much more fin material is subtracted from perforated fin designs, both their melting and solidification performances are still better than hollowed fins.

Figure 7: Variation of liquid fraction with different fin structures during solidification process.

5. Melting/Solidification Performance of LHS Tank filled via Aluminium without Fins

The melting and solidification dynamics of aluminium are different from MgCl₂. There is no need to use any heat transfer enhancement methods since the thermal conductivity of Al is already high. As seen in Figure 8, both the charging and discharging processes require less time. Melting

and solidification times are almost the same. It shows that natural convection is prominent during the melting process. Besides, both processes are much faster in comparison to cases in which MgCl₂ is employed as PCM.

Figure 8: Variation of liquid fraction of Aluminium as PCM during melting and solidification processes.

Another important detail is that the heat flux stays almost constant during most times of melting/solidification processes as in Figure 9. Although heat flux dynamics of MgCl₂ with different fin designs are not reported here, the heat flux trend of aluminium during both melting and solidification processes is desired due to heat transfer stability.

Figure 9: Variation of heat flux of Aluminium as PCM during melting and solidification processes.

6. REFERENCES

- [1] M. A. Khuda, J. Khalesi, Z. Tu, Y. Long, D. Piccioni Koch, and N. Sarunac, "Numerical analysis of a developing turbulent flow and conjugate heat transfer for molten salt and liquid sodium in a solar receiver," *Appl. Therm. Eng.*, vol. 217, no. March, 2022.
- [2] W. Zhao, D. M. France, W. Yu, T. Kim, and D. Singh, "Phase change material with graphite foam for applications in high-temperature latent heat storage systems of concentrated solar power plants," *Renew. Energy*, vol. 69, pp. 134–146, Sep. 2014.
- [3] G. Zhang et al., "Encapsulation of copper-based phase change materials for high temperature thermal energy storage," *Sol. Energy Mater. Sol. Cells*, vol. 128, pp. 131–137, 2014.
- [4] S. Tiari, S. Qiu, and M. Mahdavi, "Numerical study of finned heat pipe-assisted thermal energy storage system with high temperature phase change material," *Energy Convers. Manag.*, vol. 89, pp. 833–842, 2015.
- [5] D. Singh, T. Kim, W. Zhao, W. Yu, and D. M. France, "Development of graphite foam infiltrated with MgCl₂ for a latent heat based thermal energy storage (LHTES) system," *Renew. Energy*, vol. 94, pp. 660–667, 2016.
- [6] D. S. Jayathunga, H. P. Karunathilake, M. Narayana, and S. Witharana, "Phase change material (PCM) candidates for latent heat thermal energy storage (LHTES) in concentrated solar power (CSP) based thermal applications - A review," *Renew. Sustain. Energy Rev.*, vol. 189, no. PB, p. 113904, 2024.

Interpretation of the results (up to 400 words)

- The hollowed fin concept within a shell-and-tube LHS tank is first investigated. The importance of the location of the removal part in hollowed fin designs is reported comparing straight fin and perforated fin designs.
- Even if the same amount is removed in hollowed and perforated cases, the results approved the cruciality of the fin design on the performance of LHS tanks.
- To remove some parts of the fin structures by creating hollowed or perforated designs is very beneficial. That is because fins occupy less volume, so much more PCMs can fill the tank. Moreover, via perforated or hollowed parts of fins, natural convection circulations are not prevented during the melting process.
- Less amount of fin utilization decreases fin material costs, especially when the fin is made of Cu with coating. On the other side, removing the parts via perforating or hollowing may cause additional manufacturing costs, which are highly changeable depending on the fin material. Therefore, the concept broadens the horizon on the manufacturing side and may require techno-economical analysis as a future study topic.
- With only ~8% of fin-equipped LHS tanks, charging time roughly decreases from eight hours to six hours. Depending on the applications - CSP plants, industrial waste heat (glass, metal casting, cement industries), Carnot batteries – both finned and unfinned scenarios can be preferred.
- The outlet temperature is first discussed in order to decrease the temperature of LMs in thermocline storage tanks. Moreover, the cruciality of outlet temperature variation during charging/discharging processes is emphasized in how to design cascaded LHS tanks with gradually decreasing melting temperatures of PCMs.
- If one would like to create a cascaded LHS tank, the present study recommends using metallic PCMs instead of salt-based PCMs, even if the tanks are equipped with high-conductive fins.

However, there are not available metallic PCMs whose melting temperatures are close enough to subsequently be cascaded along the HTF tube.

-There are few structural materials currently available that can resist corrosion. The present study reports that although a coated Cu fin is offered in the present study for higher thermal conductance, low-conductive Inconel alloys have almost the same performance at higher mass flow rate conditions.

-The LHS and thermocline systems can be hybridized efficiently, with less total volume of storage media, less safety risk, and possibly less expensive ways.

Main achievements during the TNA related work (up to 250 words)

Absolutely, it was an amazing opportunity and adventure for me.

-The best thing was to experience a multicultural research environment. My next career attempt will absolutely be to have a similar study experience again.

-I learned how to manage CFD analysis in a cluster, and briefly, I took a step into the High-Performance Computing World.

-I have gained strong experience in fluid flow, heat transfer, and melting/solidification processes of PCMs in the 3D domain. This type of problem requires high computation resources. It was my first time trying to solve difficult problems.

-I have experienced how to manage scientific research solely, starting with thinking about a research topic, methods, as well as living costs, and finding a place to do all the things.

-I have met with the power of LMs. As both HTFs and storage mediums, LMs are good options for use in TES as well as thermal management applications at high temperatures.

Difficulties during the TNA related work (up to 250 words)

There was not a challenging difficulty. The errors are a part of the nature of the research process. However, all the planned CFD cases were simulated and completed.

Intended publications

On the basis of this report, the research team will discuss the results and a possible joint publication further. The general intention is to publish promising results as an article in high-impact journals in the field of energy storage and thermal sciences, such as the Journal of Energy, Journal of Energy Storage, or Journal of Heat and Mass Transfer. Afterward, the remaining results can be presented at the Congress of Thermal Sciences and Technology in Türkiye. Besides, the results can be presented at an international congress or symposium if it is funded.

Data management

The data is copied in two different portable hard-disk. One is at KIT, the other one is with me.

Conclusions / additional comments

Utilization of liquid metals and hybrid energy storage concepts are promising for future thermal technologies. The visiting researchers should be supported financially and with high motivation more.

Did you complete the EC user questionnaire available at <https://ec.europa.eu/eusurvey/runner/RIsurveyUSERS> ? (necessary)

<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No					
Feedback – HSE, Ethics and Satisfaction					
Please rate on a scale from 1 (excellent) to 5 (poor). Feel free to provide additional comments					
Practical information on how to apply for Transnational Access and the overall application process	1 (excellent)	2	3 (neutral)	4	5 (poor)
	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Information provided, once your project was accepted, on how to proceed	1 (excellent)	2	3 (neutral)	4	5 (poor)
	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Support received at the site(s) regarding technical/scientific matters and logistics	Have you got sufficient support from the RI staff during the project? If not, please, specify the problems. <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No				
RI extension / upgrades required	In your opinion, is the RI needed to be upgraded? If yes, please give an explanation. <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No				
Problems with local regulations	Have you had any problems with regulations of the visited RI owner (HSE, lab working hours, etc.)? If yes, please, specify <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No				
Health and safety issues	Did you encounter any health or safety issue during your research? Please provide details. <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No				
Environment & Ethics	Did your research involve the use of elements that may cause harm to the environment, to animals or plants? Please provide details. <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No				
Environment & Ethics	Did your research deal with endangered fauna and/or flora and/or protected areas? Please provide details. <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No				

Environment & Ethics	Did your research involve the use of elements that may cause harm to humans, including research staff? Please provide details. <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No				
Environment & Ethics – Dual use	Does your research have the potential for military applications? Please provide details. <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No				
Environment & Ethics – Misuse	Does your research have the potential for malevolent /criminal/terrorist abuse? Please provide details. <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No				
Environmental issues	Were any potentially dangerous substances (materials / gases etc.) released into the environment (atmosphere, water, or land)? Please provide details. <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No				
Ethics issues	Are there any other ethics issues that should be taken into consideration? Please specify <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No				
Overall impression of communication and interaction after finishing your TNA related work	1 (excellent)	2	3 (neutral)	4	5 (poor)
	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Suggestions for facilities not included in StoRIES which you would use for your research					
Suggestions how StoRIES can improve future TNA programme, how to make the TNA more impactful on the energy storage technologies and how to enable the achievement of high TRL levels.					
I did deep research on the internet, and by chance I found my supervisor from RI Infrastructure who suggested to look at the TNA calls. That is to say, it is not easy to know about this project. My suggestion is for RI providers to find researchers about their ongoing studies and research infrastructures.					
Feedback – Pro-active Innovation Support					

Awareness	Did you know about the pro-active innovation support of StoRIES. <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No				
Personal experience	Have you taken advantage of or benefited from the pro-active innovation support? <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No				
Information/service provided by the pro-active innovation support?	1 (excellent)	2	3 (neutral)	4	5 (poor)
	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

I declare that the above provided information and especially that information on the number of days visited the RI is correct.